

FROM THE EXPERIENCE OF USING MODERN INFORMATION AND COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY IN LITERATURE CLASSES

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Abstract The relevance of the article is determined by the introduction in the educational process of advanced pedagogical information and communication technologies. Informatization of society and education determines the need to use information and computer technology in school education. The use of modern information and computer technology at the lessons of literature is a response to the challenges of time and an effective means of increasing interest in the subject, deepening students' knowledge.

Key words: learning process, literature, modern technology, computer technology, internet

The main educational value of information technology is that it allows you to create a much brighter multisensory interactive learning environment with almost unlimited potentialities available to both the teacher and the student. In contrast to conventional technical means of education, information technology allows not only to saturate students with a large amount of knowledge, but also to develop the intellectual and creative abilities of students, their ability to independently acquire new knowledge, work with different sources of information.

The use of ICTs in the learning process contributes to an increase in the quality of knowledge of students, the level of their erudition, making it possible to organize new forms and methods of training and education. ICT can be used at different stages of the lesson: during the explanation, consolidation and generalization of educational material. The use of ICT technologies in the learning process makes it possible not only to modernize it, increase its effectiveness and motivate students, but also to differentiate the learning process, taking into account the individual characteristics of each student. The use of ICT at school should take into account the psychological characteristics of schoolchildren. ICT technologies can improve the efficiency of the educational process, provided that the teacher is well aware of the psychological and pedagogical aspects of their use [2, p. 48].

The following techniques of applying computer technology at the lessons of literature can be distinguished. With the use of a multimedia projector the teacher can demonstrate slides created in the program Microsoft Power Point,

which allows, first, significantly save time in the lesson, second, increase the brightness of the perception of the material by offering verbal, visual and musical images, third, introduce elements of amusement, liven up the learning process.

The use of audio and video material makes the literature lesson more vivid and emotional. This is aided by computer technology and its multimedia capabilities, which allow students to see the world through the eyes of artists, hear classical music, and hear professional, actor-like readings of poetry and prose. You can also take a virtual excursion to the homeland of the writer or poet, visit his museum (for example, in the Lermontov museum-reserve Tarkhany, in the birthplace of A. Pushkin, A.N. Ostrovsky State Museum-Reserve, etc.), hear a masterful reading of favorite classic works, get acquainted with critical materials, find the necessary information and texts on the Internet.

Watching fragments of the film makes the students look at the work in a new way, the visualization of the characters makes them closer and clearer, many have a desire to reread the work and compare the film with the text.

The most important use of information technology in the learning and educational process is also the project activities of students. Performance of pupils' works in the form of presentations and reports with the help of computer programs allows forming and developing skills of self-education of schoolchildren, corresponds to the methodology of scientific cognition, provides mastering knowledge not on reproductive, but on creative level [3, p.10].

Computer technology provides a wide range of opportunities for the development of creative potential of schoolchildren. A teacher can teach a child to use a computer competently. With the skillful guidance of a teacher, a teenager learns among the abundance of information on the Internet to find the right one, learns to process this information, which is the most important task.

Thus, the use of modern information technologies in schools allows teachers to change the content, methods and organizational forms of education qualitatively. The innovative approach to the system of education and upbringing develops such qualities in students as the desire for new experiences, creativity and criticism, fosters faith in the future.

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